

Tribal Culture And Conservation of Biodiversity For Sustainable Livelihood: An appraisal reference with special reference to Tiwa tribe of Assam

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There is a growing concern among the technocrats, bureaucrats, politicians etc. to protect and improve the quality of environmental resources such as air, water, soil, vegetation and minerals, through various measures. Such steps become absolutely necessary in the countries where advanced level of institutional and technological set-up exists. It is noteworthy that certain tribal areas as well as remote rural areas of India have better environmental quality and balance. This can be evidenced by the Tiwa tribe of Assam. Their lifestyle and less availability of modern technological means shows a close connection with nature, which contributes to a healthy ecosystem. Some of their religious practices have been proven to enhance and promote biodiversity. Their traditional skills and techniques provide valuable information to the global community and a useful model for biodiversity policies. Herean effort has been made to see how Tiwas' socio-cultural traits help in sustaining the eco-system as well as its importance in the present global environment.

Keywords: Tiwa, biodiversity, technology, lifestyle, ecosystem.